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THE USE OF ENGLISH PROVERBS AND SAYINGS FOR A FOREIGN LANGUAGE STUDY IN NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. This article is devoted to the use of modern interactive – communicative method of teaching a foreign language in a higher educational institution. The purpose of the article is to review and analyze the use of paremias (proverbs and sayings) in foreign language classes using the example of teaching English. Comparison with analogues in the Russian language helps to form a cognitive interest in learning English, develop imaginative thinking, creative inclinations, language guesswork, memory and logic, expand knowledge about the culture of English-speaking countries, expand horizons.

The article covers the effective use of proverbs and sayings in teaching a foreign language, for students of a non-linguistic university. The author considers the tasks that need to be solved during the educational process to achieve optimal results, justifies the feasibility, effectiveness and relevance of their use for teaching foreign languages in higher education.

In the article, the author cites studies by well-known linguists on the effectiveness of using proverbs and sayings in foreign language lessons, and also presents the results of a study on the use of these tools to increase student interest and effectiveness in teaching foreign languages. Particular attention is paid to the use of proverbs and sayings when practicing listening, speaking, reading and writing skills. The article provides examples of the use of educational techniques for teaching students a foreign language, aimed at developing communication abilities for using the language in natural situations of communication in the field of tourism and hospitality.

Key words: interactive communication methodology, communication skills, teaching foreign languages in higher education, tourism and hospitality, foreign communication, paremias, proverbs and sayings, distance learning

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ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКИХ ПОСЛОВИЦ И ПОГОВОРК В ОБУЧЕНИИ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ В НЕЯЗЫКОВОМ УНИВЕРСИТЕТЕ

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Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена применению современной интерактивно-коммуникативной методики преподавания иностранного языка в высшем учебном заведении. Цель статьи – обзор и анализ применения паремий (пословиц и поговорок) на занятиях иностранного языка на примере преподавания английского языка. Сравнение с аналогами в русском языке помогает формировать познавательный интерес к изучению английского языка, развивать образное мышление, творческие задатки, языковую догадку, память и логику, расширять знания о культуре англоязычных стран и кругозор. В статье освещаются вопросы эффективного использования пословиц и поговорок в обучении иностранному языку для студентов неязыкового вуза. Автором рассматриваются задачи, которые необходимо решать в ходе учебного процесса для достижения оптимальных результатов, обосновывается целесообразность, эффективность и актуальность их использования в преподавании иностранных языков в высшей школе. В статье автор проводит обзор теоретических трудов известных исследователей в области теории и методики преподавания иностранных языков об эффективности применения пословиц и поговорок, а также предоставляет результаты исследования по использованию данных средств для повышения интереса студентов в преподавании иностранных языков. Особое внимание уделяется применению пословиц и поговорок при отработке навыков аудирования, говорения, чтения и письма. В статье приводятся примеры применения образовательных приемов для обучения студентов иностранному языку, направленных на развитие коммуникативных способностей для использования языка в естественных ситуациях общения в сфере туризма и гостеприимства.

Ключевые слова: интерактивно-коммуникативная методика, коммуникативные навыки, преподавание иностранных языков в высшей школе, туризм и гостеприимство, иноязычная коммуникация, паремии, пословицы и поговорки, дистанционное обучение

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Introduction

The system of teaching foreign languages at the university in the 1980–1990s was due to the discrepancy between the order of social changes and the level of training of the graduates. The didactic potential of interactive – communicative method is presented for teaching communication activities. The results obtained give an overview of modern technologies for teaching a foreign language obtained in the course of classroom and independent work of students, as well as in the format of distance learning [7, c. 166]. «The area of interest of scientists is the study of those aspects of professional consciousness that allow a person to be successful in educational and professional activities» [5, c. 3]. The success of contacts with representatives of other cultural groups is determined by the following factors: openness and benevolence, atmosphere of psychological comfort, ability to develop and establish good personal relationships. «It is becoming important to provide conditions that will help new generation specialists not only master modern technologies and the basics of business communication and acquire the ability to use soft skills, but also focus on the self-development and development of an individual original work style» [4, p. 68].

The great Czech teacher Jan Amos Komenský believed that the study of a foreign language should follow the path from the gradual comprehension of the foreign language statement meaning to the beauty perception of words, expressions, the richness of all linguistic possibilities and, finally, to language treasury mastery and to the ability to penetrate the aesthetic essence of the language. The comprehension of a foreign language should be not only pragmatic, but also spiritual. Developing Komenský's ideas, K.D. Ushinsky wrote that it is necessary to teach not only speaking, but also the culture of the country of the language, it is necessary to acquaint students with the customs, art and literature. Professor M.G. Gazilov wrote: «It should be noted that the features of national identity are reflected primarily in proverbs and sayings, in songs, as well as in works of fiction, i. e. in the language» [3, p. 55].

Theory analysis

In the twentieth century, the mechanism of this cultural phenomenon has not fundamentally changed. The process of folklore creativity is continuous. The proverb should be concise, contextually flexible and meaningful, it should generalize the situation giving

moral advice. Therefore, by studying English proverbs and sayings and comparing them with Russian ones we get the opportunity to significantly improve our knowledge of English, get acquainted with customs and the history of England, as well as enrich our native language, teach students to understand folk wisdom, introduce them to universal human moral values.

Moral ideals reflected in folklore aphorisms are of great importance in the formation of characteristic socio-historical types both in real life and in the cultural thinking of the people. In this sense, English proverbs and sayings serve as a key to the correct perception of the characteristics of the English language. Studying the English lifestyle, character and language, we should necessarily refer to proverbs and sayings as the most valuable examples of the language.

Some of the oldest English idioms have their origin from figurative moral advice and enduring comparisons that come from ancient Anglo-Saxon times.

Proverbs and sayings go back to ancient times. Many of them appeared even when there was no writing. Therefore, the primary sources are unknown. English proverbs and sayings are mostly of literary, folk and biblical origin.

Proverbs and sayings were used in the teaching of a foreign language, such as Latin, in medieval Europe, and nowadays there is no language course completed without their help. According to T.V. Ustinova, the key elements of professional multilingual/multicultural thinking include openness and worldview curiosity, orientation on the recognition of cultural diversity and purposeful interrelated repertoire of several languages [12].

A teacher should draw students' attention to films, songs, sayings and proverbs in a foreign language. They all stimulate independent activities of students, increasing interest and psychological readiness to perceive new information. In addition, a teacher can recommend students various types of activities, such as listening to audio recordings, reading interesting articles on certain topics, watching videos possibly devoted to holidays and different events.

A communicative-cognitive approach is developing in the methodology of AI training. This approach is implemented in the methodological systems of teaching a foreign language as a second and in the system of multilingual education, manifesting where there are «grounds for searching on a conscious basis similarities

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and differences between the language systems of the native, first and second foreign language» [2, с. 48].

The communicative method solves not only specific language challenges, such as overcoming the language barrier. He motivates to study cultural differences, features of foreign language communication, develops ability to think in a foreign language. Classes according to this method, they are held in a lively, emotional atmosphere. Even at the entry level, students can not only read or write, but are also able to verbally express their opinion within a certain set of topics, understand authentic speech. [8, p.88]

To develop the language skills of students you can use English rhymes or songs containing new foreign words. Special techniques for remembering words should also be used. Some of them include pronouncing in different tones and rhythmic pronunciation on any familiar motive.

The lexical picturesque and poetic precision of proverbs and sayings allows them to be used when explaining and practicing some grammatical phenomena and enriching the vocabulary of students. Proverbs and sayings can be used in speech practice exercises as an incentive.

The same proverb or saying can be interpreted in different ways. Therefore, based on a particular proverb or saying, students learn to express their own thoughts, feelings, experiences, i. e. demonstrate different ways of placing them in speech. So the use of proverbs and sayings at the lessons of a foreign language develops the creative initiative of students through prepared and unprepared speech. According to the old English proverb, «A good expression is always to the point». [5].

Everyone who addresses folklore genres, including paremias, when studying a foreign language and culture, shares this idea. Paremias is the whole complex of proverbs and sayings of a particular language.

Linguists study such paremias as English sayings and proverbs. Psychologists find certain features of human thinking in the process of creating a proverb. Historians register the most important changes in customs, traditions, tracing the development of the paremic fund in different cultures.

The remark «Watch your steps!» is usually taken literally. However, today this expression is increasingly used figuratively as a moral warning. Perhaps we are witnessing the birth of a new paremia, typical of our days.

Linguists studying proverbs and sayings pay attention to the linguistic principles of their formation. Folklorists and ethnographers attempt to make a connection between a national character and the content of a proverb.

John Mapletoft, the author of one of the oldest collections of English proverbs (1707) said: «Proverbs reflect the passage of time and anyone who wants to see themselves in them as in a mirror» [9].

A vivid palette of folk proverbs is presented in the works of Jeffrey Chaucer, the founder of English national literature.

Paremia are diverse and timeless. Indeed, no matter what time we live, proverbs and sayings always remain relevant. They reflect the rich historical experience of nations, ideas related to labor activity, culture and life of peoples. The appropriate use of proverbs and sayings gives a unique expressiveness and originality.

Russian linguist Zhigulev writes that proverbs and sayings illustrate the lifestyle, geographical position of the country, its history, traditions, culture, socio-cultural layer for centuries and respond to changes in the social and cultural life of the people. The proverbs briefly and figuratively reflect the system of values, public morality, ethics, attitude to the world, to other peoples, instructions for all cases, which constitutes a high educational potential for their use in training.

Students are offered to analyze the similarity and difference in the linguistic design of a saying or proverb, to give examples of a specific contextual use of paremia in addition to translating and selecting a Russian analogue. An interesting aspect of the work is the attempts of students to conduct an etymological and historical study of a particular proverb or saying.

Each paremia contains certain lexical, phonetic and grammatical material, the same proverb or saying can be included in several groups. Often, the proverbs that are given to students for articulation and intonation training are later studied at a higher level of language training when a teacher introduces new vocabulary or new grammatical structures.

Unfortunately, at the university in the course of English for tourism and hospitality, they don't pay enough attention to proverbs and sayings. However, they can be used in any aspect of the study: articulation and intonation work, study and practice of new lexical units, grammatical phenomena, extracurricular work on various linguistic topics.

Proverbs should be distinguished from sayings. The main features of proverbs are their didactic content and completeness. Sayings are distinguished by the lack of instructive character and the incompleteness of the conclusion.

Sayings and proverbs are a widespread genre of oral folk art. Such expressive means as simple form, exact rhyme, brevity made proverbs and sayings memorable, persistent and necessary in speech.

Proverbs and sayings are set expressions. When we use a set expression, we can include it in any sentence or statement and combine it with neutral vocabulary.

Proverbs and sayings are different linguistic phenomena.

Proverb is considered as «small folklore genres» which is a kind of completed saying, characterized by brevity, a certain rhythm and sometimes rhyme. The proverb teaches, advises, reminds, generalizes, characterizes. It is a kind of conclusion.

In linguistics there is one very important and interesting theory. It is not supported by all linguists, but some still approve. Proverbs are nothing more than «phraseological expressions». This is the fourth grammatical type of phraseological units in addition to phraseological unities, fusions and combinations. Phraseological expressions are characterized by self-sufficiency and completeness. This idea was developed by Shansky and supported by Vinogradov. The proverb is considered as one of the types of phraseological units and therefore should be studied in phraseology.

Saying is another small genre of folklore. It is also a type of additional language unit, which interferes phraseology on more decisive rights. Saying is one of the types of phraseologisms that has an intermediate position between the proverb and the short phraseologism itself. But a saying has a fundamental difference that distinguishes it from a proverb. They should not be confused in any case. A proverb does not have a sign of completeness and generalization.

«The creative process is facilitated by the alternation of group and individual activities, work in pairs, an exchange of views and a dialogue with oneself. The realization will come that students know, know how. They will be able to evaluate their capabilities and deepen their knowledge» [10, p.86].

The use of proverbs and sayings on the lessons of foreign language

The knowledge of English proverbs and sayings develops memory, enriches the vocabulary of

students, helps them learn the figurative structure of the language and introduces to folk wisdom. In some figurative sentences containing a finished thought new words are usually easier to remember.

For example, the work of memorizing numbers usually causes difficulty for students, but proverbs and sayings that include numbers can help to remember:

Rain before seven, fine before eleven.

A cat has nine lives.

Two in distress makes sorrow less.

Four is company, but one is none.

Rain before seven, fine before eleven

One head is good but two are better.

Each proverb has its own objective.

Proverbs

1. Give advice:

Don't trouble troubles until trouble troubles you.

2. Teach wisdom:

Who gossips with you will gossip about you.

3. Ridicule:

Everyone calls his own geese swans.

4. Comment on the appearance:

You look like a cat after it has eaten a canary.

5. Philosophize:

Liars should have good memories

6. Summarize people's experience:

The road to hell is paved with good intentions.

7. Warn:

If you sing before breakfast, you will cry before night.

Special attention should be paid to those expressive means which help to memorize proverbs and sayings.

One of them is an exact rhyme:

A stitch in time saves nine.

Birds of a feather flock together.

Little strokes fell great oaks.

More haste, less speed.

Easy come easy go.

Like father, like son.

An exact rhyme and brevity are significant aspects of the memorability of statements, most of proverbs and sayings contain no more than five words:

Girls will be girls.

Better late than never.

Dead man tells nothing.

Proverbs and sayings can also be used as phonetic warming up.

a

My cat is black,

*My cat is fat.
My cat likes rats
Rats are fat.*

th[θ]

1. *I thought, I thought of thinking of thanking you!*
2. *Not these things here but those things there!*
3. *The thirty thousand thieves
thought they thrilled the throne
throughout Thursday.*

English Proverbs and Sayings can be a good example of effective usage while teaching students basic grammar. They help to remember various grammatical constructions and forms, especially when they are used in new grammar structures and exercises.

While studying the topic Present Simple the proverbs and sayings can help to remember the using of the verb with the third-person singular (**he, she, it**).

If we use a verb with the third-person singular, we need to make another change with the verb. We add the **-s** or **-es** endings.

April shower brings May flower – Great ships ask deep water.- An action speaks louder than a word.

Conditional Sentences

If the blind lead the blind both shall fall into the ditch.

If you want things well done, do it yourselves.

If we cannot do as we would, we must do as we can.

Modal Verbs.

You cannot wash charcoal blue.

Love can't be bought.

If you have made your bed, you must lie on it.

A man must do as he may, not as he would.

The Infinitive

To build a fire under yourself.

To lay for rainy days.

To call off the dog.

To buy pigs in pokes.

The Article

Cats in gloves catch no mouse.

A clean hand wants no washing.

A cow has short horns.

A good dog deserves a sweet bone.

A friend in need is a friend indeed.

Degrees of comparison of adjectives

Two heads are better than one.

There are no friends as faithful as good books.

Better late than never.

In English classes, you can offer the following tasks to develop spoken language skills:

1. *Make a dialogue with a proverb.*
2. *Compose situations with proverbs or sayings.*
3. *Describe the picture with the use of a proverb.*
4. *Make a plan for the text.*
5. *Compose a story using given proverbs.*

At the beginning of the lesson, a proverb can motivate students to discuss the topic.

Proverbs and sayings can be used as a basis for starting a discussion. They can be used to student performance. Proverbs and sayings are short and succinct expressions. They can be used as an introduction to the lesson, as a preparatory stage of the lesson or in the main part of the lesson as a means of activating lexical units, introduction to listening or reading. In addition, sayings and proverbs can help expand linguistic knowledge.

«Comparison of the native language with a foreign language is inevitable due to the imposition of new linguistic realities on the already existing and firmly entrenched in the student's mind. The study of a foreign language, not focused on comparing it with his native language, is impossible, since the very fact of recognition of learning a foreign language in isolation from his native language indicates the absence of a linguistic basis for transmitting new linguistic information» [1, p.2].

In this article, we found that the use of English proverbs and sayings is an effective method of working in English lessons, in particular for the development of lexical skills of students at the senior level. Since the use of English proverbs and sayings is creative work, students with great interest perform such tasks. In addition, since proverbs and sayings are a multifunctional methodological tool in teaching English, students will be able to develop all language skills in English lessons using proverbs and sayings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it should be noted that working with proverbs and sayings in English lessons not only helps to diversify the educational process and make it more vivid and interesting. It helps to solve a number of very important educational problems.

The study of paremia, their analysis and comparison with analogues in their native language helps to form in children a cognitive interest in the studied subject and culture of English-speaking countries, expand their horizons and develop imaginative thinking, creative

inclinations, language guesswork, as well as attention, memory and logic. In addition, it creates the possibility of broad cross-subject connections and generates interest in research work in the framework of student scientific projects.

Scientists comprehend aspect of specialization of professional and methodical consciousness of the applicant of a foreign language quite deeply and in detail. A foreign language as an educational area dictates this specialization. It predefines learning parameters foreign language, the specifics

of the teacher's perception of the environment of the world and positioning oneself in it. Based on these features, scientists call methodological consciousness intercultural; it is pre-knowledge, awareness and understanding of relationships (similarities and differences) between the culture of their home country and the countries of the language taught. We are talking about the formation of the ability of the teacher to go beyond their culture, ability to self-change in the process of dating with a different culture [11].

Список источников

1. Аллен, Е. П. Этнолингвистический экскурс в историю современного английского языка. // Иностранные языки в школе – 2022.–№ 5. – С.
2. Бим, И. Л. Концепция обучения второму иностранному языку (немецкому на базе английского). – Обнинск: Титул, 2001. – 48 с.
3. Газилов, М. Г. Сравнительное исследование особенностей выражения национальной идентичности в русском и французском языках. // Сервис plus. – 2019. – Т. 13. – № 3. – С. 55.
4. Груздева, М. В., Газилов, М. Г., Логинова, Н. Ю., Костоварова, В. В. Развитие творческого потенциала студентов в неязыковом вузе на занятиях по иностранному языку // Сервис plus. – 2021. – Т. 15. – № 4. – С. 68.
5. История возникновения пословиц и поговорок – режим доступа: <https://multiurok.ru/files/istoriia-vozniknoveniia-poslovits-i-pogovorok.html>
6. Капаса, А., Пей, Дж. Теория мышления и школьная психология // Канадский журнал школьной психологии. – 2021, 27 октября – с. 3.
7. Костоварова, В. В. Цифровые образовательные технологии в обучении иностранному языку в университете туризма и гостеприимства. // Сервис Plus, том 16, № 2. 2022, 166 с.
8. Макарова, А. И. (2021). Применение песенного содержания в обучении второму иностранному языку (на примере французских песен). Сервис Plus, 15 (3), 86–96. – С. 88.
9. Маплетофтом, Джон. Избранные пословицы: итальянские, испанские, французские, английские, шотландские, британские, и др. В основном морального характера. Иностранные языки, переведенные на английский язык, 1631–1721.
10. Спатарь-Козаченко. Технология педагогической мастерской построения знаний на уроке испанского языка. // Вестник ассоциации вузов туризма и сервиса – 2016 – Т.10. – № 1 – с. 86.
11. Ульянова, Л. А. Технологии формирования интеркультурного сознания будущего учителя иностранного языка // Вестник Костромского государственного университета. Серия: Педагогика. Психология. Социокинетика. – 2018. – Т. 24. – № 1. – С. 114–116.
12. Устинова, Т. В. Плюрилингвистика и обучение учителей второго языка // Филологический класс. – 2021. – 26 (1). – р. 273–280.

References

1. Allen, E. P. (2022). Etnolingvisticheskiy ekskurs v istoriiu sovremennogo angliiskogo iazyka [Ethnolinguistic excursion into the history of modern English]. *Inostrannyye yazyki v shkole* [Foreign languages at school], 5, 30–39. (In Russ.).
2. Bim, I. L. (2001). *Kontseptciia obucheniia vtoromu inostrannomu iazyku (nemetckomu na baze angliiskogo)* [The concept of teaching a second foreign language (German based on English)]. Obninsk: Title. (In Russ.).
3. Gazilov, M. G. (2019). Comparative study on peculiarities of expressing the national identity in Russian and French. *Service plus*, 13(3), 51–57. DOI: 10.24411/2413-693X-2019-10306 (In Russ.)

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4. Gazilov, M. G., Loginova, N. Yu., Gruzdeva, M. V. & Kostovarova, V. V. (2021). Development of the creativity of students in a non-linguistic university in foreign language classes. *Service plus*, 15(4), 66–76. DOI: 10.24412/2413-693X-2021-4-66-76 (In Russ.).
5. *Istoriia vozniknoveniia poslovits i pogovorok [The history of proverbs and sayings]*. URL: <https://multiurok.ru/files/istoriia-vozniknoveniia-poslovits-i-pogovorok.html>. (Accessed on July, 03, 2025.) (In Russ.).
6. Kapasi, A., Pei, J. (2021). Mindset theory and school psychology. *Canadian Journal of School Psychology*, 37(1), 1–18.
7. Kostovarova, V. V. (2022). Digital educational technologies in teaching foreign languages at the university of tourism and hospitality. *Service plus*, 16(2), 54–63. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6964020. (In Russ.).
8. Makarova, A. I. (2021). Application of song content in the second foreign language classes (on the example of French songs). *Service plus*, 15 (3), 86–96. DOI: 10.24412/2413-693X-2021-3-86-96. (In Russ.).
9. Mapletoft, J. (2025). Select proverbs, Italian, Spanish, French, English, Scottish, British, &c. chiefly moral. The foreign languages done into English. London: Printed by J. H. for P. Monckton.
10. Spatar-Kozachenko, T. I. (2016). Tekhnologiya pedagogicheskoi masterskoi postroeniia znaniia na uroke ispanskogo iazyka [Technology of Pedagogical Workshop of Building Knowledge in the Lesson of Spanish]. *Vestnik assotciatsii vuzov turizma i servisa [Universities for Tourism and Service Association Bulletin]*, 10(1), 85–91. (In Russ.).
11. Ulyanova, L. A. (2018). Tekhnologii formirovaniia interkulturnogo soznaniia budushchego uchitelia inostrannogo iazyka [Technologies for the formation of intercultural consciousness of the future teacher of a foreign language]. *Vestnik Kostromskogo gosudarstvennogo universiteta. Seriya: Pedagogika. Psikhologiya. Sociokinetika [Bulletin of Kostroma State University. Series: Pedagogy. Psychology. Social Kinetics]*, 24(1), 114–116. (In Russ.).
12. Ustinova, T. V. (2021). Pliur lingvistika i obuchenie uchitelei vtorogo iazyka [Plurilingualism and the second language teacher education]. *Filologicheskii klass [Philological Class]*, 26 (1), 273–280. (In Russ.).